

Evaluation of Opioid Sparing Analgesia Techniques in Postoperative Pain Management

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Abstract:

Background: The opioid epidemic has intensified the need for effective alternatives to traditional opioid-based postoperative pain management. This study evaluated the efficacy of opioid-sparing analgesia compared to conventional fentanyl and morphine-based approaches.

Methods: A randomized controlled trial was conducted, enrolling 200 patients undergoing major surgery. Patients were randomized to receive either opioid-sparing analgesia (n=100) or opioid-based pain management (n=100). The primary outcome was 48-hour postoperative opioid consumption. Secondary outcomes included pain scores, adverse events, recovery metrics, and patient satisfaction.

Results: The opioid-sparing group demonstrated significantly lower opioid consumption (median 30 vs. 60 mg OMEs, p<0.001), pain scores (mean difference 0.9-1.2 points, p<0.001), and opioid-related adverse events (nausea: 15% vs. 29%, p=0.016; sedation: 11% vs. 22%, p=0.035). Recovery was accelerated in the opioid-sparing group, with earlier ambulation (median 18 vs. 24 hours, p<0.001) and shorter hospital stays (median 3 vs. 4 days, p<0.001). Patient satisfaction was significantly higher in the opioid-sparing group (55% vs. 40% very satisfied, p=0.002).

Conclusion: Opioid-sparing analgesia demonstrated superior outcomes compared to opioid-based approaches, supporting its implementation as a standard approach for postoperative pain management.

Keywords: Opioid-sparing analgesia; Multimodal pain management; Postoperative pain; Patient satisfaction; Recovery outcomes.

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Introduction

Postoperative pain management is a crucial aspect of patient care, as inadequate pain control can lead to prolonged recovery, increased morbidity, and reduced patient satisfaction [1]. Opioids have long been the mainstay of postoperative pain management due to their potent analgesic effects. However, the widespread use of opioids has contributed to the current opioid epidemic, with increased rates of opioid misuse, addiction, and overdose deaths [2]. Moreover, opioids are associated with various side effects, such as respiratory depression, nausea, vomiting, constipation, and sedation, which can hinder recovery and prolong hospital stays [3].

Given the challenges associated with opioid use, there has been a growing interest in opioid-sparing analgesia techniques for postoperative pain management. Opioid-sparing analgesia refers to the use of non-opioid analgesics, regional anesthesia techniques, and other adjuvant therapies to minimize opioid consumption while still providing adequate pain relief [4]. The goal of opioid-sparing analgesia is to reduce the risk of opioid-related

adverse events, improve patient outcomes, and facilitate faster recovery.

Multimodal analgesia is a key component of opioid-sparing analgesia techniques. This approach involves the use of multiple analgesic agents with different mechanisms of action to target pain pathways at various levels [5]. By combining different classes of analgesics, such as nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), acetaminophen, gabapentinoids, and local anesthetics, multimodal analgesia can provide effective pain relief while reducing opioid requirements [6]. Studies have shown that multimodal analgesia is associated with reduced postoperative pain scores, decreased opioid consumption, and improved patient satisfaction compared to opioid-based analgesia alone [7,8].

Regional anesthesia techniques, such as peripheral nerve blocks and neuraxial anesthesia, are another important component of opioid-sparing analgesia. These techniques involve the administration of local anesthetics near the nerves or the spinal cord

to provide targeted pain relief [9]. Peripheral nerve blocks, such as femoral nerve blocks for knee surgery or interscalene blocks for shoulder surgery, can provide effective analgesia while minimizing systemic opioid exposure [10]. Similarly, neuraxial techniques, such as epidural analgesia, can provide excellent pain control for major abdominal and thoracic surgeries, reducing the need for opioids and their associated side effects [11].

In addition to multimodal analgesia and regional anesthesia, other adjuvant therapies have been investigated for their opioid-sparing potential. These include the use of ketamine, an NMDA receptor antagonist, which has been shown to reduce postoperative opioid consumption and improve pain scores [12]. Alpha-2 agonists, such as dexmedetomidine and clonidine, have also been used as adjuvants to reduce opioid requirements and provide sedation [13]. Furthermore, non-pharmacological interventions, such as acupuncture, transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS), and cognitive-behavioral therapy, have been explored as complementary approaches to reduce pain and opioid use [14].

Despite the promising evidence supporting opioid-sparing analgesia techniques, their widespread adoption in clinical practice has been limited by various factors. These include the lack of standardized protocols, inadequate training and education of healthcare providers, and concerns about the safety and efficacy of non-opioid analgesics [15]. Moreover, the optimal combination of analgesic agents and techniques for different surgical procedures and patient populations remains to be determined.

In conclusion, the evaluation of opioid-sparing analgesia techniques in postoperative pain management is a critical area of research, given the pressing need to address the opioid epidemic and improve patient outcomes. By combining multimodal analgesia, regional anesthesia, and adjuvant therapies, opioid-sparing analgesia has the potential to provide effective pain relief while minimizing opioid-related adverse events. However, further research is needed to establish evidence-based guidelines and protocols for the implementation of opioid-sparing analgesia in clinical practice.

Aims and Objectives

The primary aim of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of opioid-sparing analgesia techniques in postoperative pain management. The specific objectives were to assess the impact of multimodal analgesia, regional anesthesia, and adjuvant therapies on postoperative pain scores, opioid consumption, and opioid-related adverse events compared to traditional opioid-based analgesia. Additionally, the study aimed to identify

the optimal combination of analgesic agents and techniques for different surgical procedures and patient populations.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: The investigators conducted this prospective, randomized, controlled trial at the Department of Anaesthesiology at a tertiary care centre between September 2020 and September 2021. The research team obtained written informed consent from all participants after providing detailed explanations of the study procedures, risks, and benefits.

Patient Population and Selection Criteria: The research team screened all adult patients scheduled for elective major surgical procedures at the medical centre for potential participation. The study included patients aged between 18 and 80 years who were scheduled for major abdominal, thoracic, orthopedic, or gynecological surgeries requiring postoperative hospitalization of at least 48 hours. Eligible participants possessed American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status classifications I through III and were able to understand and comply with study protocols. The investigators excluded patients who reported chronic opioid use (defined as daily opioid consumption for more than three months prior to surgery), had documented allergies to any study medications, exhibited severe renal dysfunction (estimated glomerular filtration rate < 30 mL/min/1.73m²), demonstrated significant hepatic impairment (Child-Pugh class B or C), suffered from chronic pain conditions requiring regular analgesic use, had a history of substance abuse, showed cognitive impairment affecting their ability to use patient-controlled analgesia, or were unable to provide informed consent. Additionally, pregnant or lactating women, patients with contraindications to regional anesthesia, and those participating in other clinical trials were excluded from participation.

Sample Size Determination and Randomization: The investigators calculated the required sample size based on previously published data indicating a standard deviation of 20mg in 48-hour oral morphine equivalent consumption. To detect a clinically significant difference of 30% in postoperative opioid consumption between groups, with a power of 80% and a two-sided alpha level of 0.05, the study required 91 patients per group. Accounting for potential dropouts and protocol violations, the research team increased the sample size to 100 patients per group, resulting in a total enrollment target of 200 patients. A biostatistician not involved in patient care generated the randomization sequence using computer software (SAS version 9.4, SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA), employing a block randomization strategy

with variable block sizes of 6 and 9. The allocation ratio was 1:1 for the opioid-sparing analgesia group, fentanyl and morphine group. The research coordinator maintained the randomization sequence and prepared sequentially numbered, opaque, sealed envelopes containing group assignments. These envelopes remained secured in the research office and were opened only after obtaining informed consent and confirming all inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Results

The study analyzed data from 200 participants equally distributed across two groups: opioid-sparing analgesia (n=100) and opioid control (n=100). The demographic and clinical characteristics demonstrated no significant differences between the two groups in terms of age, sex distribution, body mass index, ASA physical status, types of surgery, or duration of surgical procedures (all $p > 0.05$), indicating successful randomization (Table 1).

The analysis of the primary outcome revealed significantly lower postoperative opioid consumption in the opioid-sparing analgesia group compared to the control group. The median oral morphine equivalents (OMEs) consumption was 30 mg (IQR: 18-48) in the opioid-sparing group, compared to 60 mg (IQR: 40-90) in the opioid control group ($p < 0.001$) (Table 2).

Postoperative pain scores, assessed using the numeric rating scale (0-10), were consistently lower in the opioid-sparing analgesia group across all time points (Table 3). At 6 hours post-surgery, the mean pain score was 3.2 ± 1.4 in the opioid-sparing group, compared to 4.1 ± 1.6 in the control group ($p < 0.001$). This trend continued throughout the 48-hour observation period, with the opioid-sparing group maintaining significantly lower pain scores at 12 hours (2.8 ± 1.3 vs. 3.7 ± 1.5), 24

hours (2.4 ± 1.1 vs. 3.2 ± 1.3), and 48 hours (1.9 ± 0.9 vs. 2.6 ± 1.2) post-surgery (all $p < 0.001$).

The incidence of opioid-related adverse events was notably lower in the opioid-sparing analgesia group (Table 4). Nausea occurred in 15% of patients in the opioid-sparing group compared to 29% in the control group ($p = 0.016$). Similarly, vomiting was observed in 9% of opioid-sparing group patients versus 19% in the control group ($p = 0.041$). Sedation rates were also significantly lower in the opioid-sparing group (11%) compared to the control group (22%) ($p = 0.035$). The incidence of pruritus and respiratory depression did not differ significantly between the groups ($p = 0.085$ and $p = 0.174$, respectively).

Recovery milestones demonstrated significant advantages in the opioid-sparing group (Table 5). The median time to first ambulation was shorter in the opioid-sparing group at 18 hours (IQR: 12-24) compared to 24 hours (IQR: 18-36) in the control group ($p < 0.001$). Length of hospital stay was also reduced in the opioid-sparing group, with a median of 3 days (IQR: 2-4) versus 4 days (IQR: 3-5) in the control group ($p < 0.001$).

Patient satisfaction metrics revealed higher satisfaction levels in the opioid-sparing analgesia group (Table 6). The proportion of patients reporting being "very satisfied" was significantly higher in the opioid-sparing group (55%) compared to the control group (40%) ($p = 0.002$). The mean satisfaction score was also significantly higher in the opioid-sparing group (4.3 ± 0.8) compared to the control group (3.9 ± 1.1) ($p = 0.003$).

These results collectively demonstrated superior outcomes in the opioid-sparing analgesia group across all measured parameters, including reduced opioid consumption, improved pain control, fewer adverse events, faster recovery, and higher patient satisfaction compared to both traditional opioid-based approaches.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	Opioid-Sparing Analgesia (n=100)	Opioid Control (n=100)	P-value
Age (years), mean \pm SD	54.1 \pm 13.2	53.8 \pm 14.6	0.876
Sex (male), n (%)	51 (51.0)	49 (49.0)	0.777
BMI (kg/m ²), mean \pm SD	27.5 \pm 4.9	28.3 \pm 5.2	0.261
ASA physical status, n (%)			0.921
I	23 (23.0)	22 (22.0)	
II	60 (60.0)	62 (62.0)	
III	17 (17.0)	16 (16.0)	
Type of surgery, n (%)			0.979
Abdominal	41 (41.0)	40 (40.0)	
Thoracic	14 (14.0)	15 (15.0)	
Orthopedic	31 (31.0)	30 (30.0)	
Gynecological	14 (14.0)	15 (15.0)	
Duration of surgery (min), median (IQR)	120 (85-150)	125 (90-155)	0.382

Table 2: Postoperative Opioid Consumption

Outcome	Opioid-Sparing Analgesia (n=100)	Opioid Control (n=100)	P-value
OMEs (mg), median (IQR)	30 (18-48)	60 (40-90)	<0.001*

Significant difference between opioid-sparing vs. control group (p<0.001)

Table 3: Postoperative Pain Scores

Time Point	Opioid-Sparing Analgesia (n=100)	Opioid Control (n=100)	P-value
6 hours, mean \pm SD	3.2 \pm 1.4	4.1 \pm 1.6	<0.001*
12 hours, mean \pm SD	2.8 \pm 1.3	3.7 \pm 1.5	<0.001*
24 hours, mean \pm SD	2.4 \pm 1.1	3.2 \pm 1.3	<0.001*
48 hours, mean \pm SD	1.9 \pm 0.9	2.6 \pm 1.2	<0.001*

Significant difference between opioid-sparing vs. control group (p<0.001)

Table 4: Incidence of Opioid-Related Adverse Events

Adverse Event	Opioid-Sparing Analgesia (n=100)	Opioid Control (n=100)	P-value
Nausea, n (%)	15 (15.0)	29 (29.0)	0.016*
Vomiting, n (%)	9 (9.0)	19 (19.0)	0.041*
Pruritus, n (%)	6 (6.0)	13 (13.0)	0.085
Sedation, n (%)	11 (11.0)	22 (22.0)	0.035*
Respiratory depression, n (%)	1 (1.0)	4 (4.0)	0.174

Significant difference between opioid-sparing vs. control group

Table 5: Time to First Ambulation and Length of Hospital Stay

Outcome	Opioid-Sparing Analgesia (n=100)	Opioid Control (n=100)	P-value
Time to first ambulation (hours), median (IQR)	18 (12-24)	24 (18-36)	<0.001*
Length of hospital stay (days), median (IQR)	3 (2-4)	4 (3-5)	<0.001*

Significant difference between opioid-sparing vs. control group (p<0.001)

Table 6: Patient Satisfaction with Pain Management

Satisfaction Level	Opioid-Sparing Analgesia (n=100)	Opioid Control (n=100)	P-value
Very satisfied, n (%)	55 (55.0)	40 (40.0)	0.002*
Satisfied, n (%)	35 (35.0)	34 (34.0)	
Neutral, n (%)	8 (8.0)	14 (14.0)	
Dissatisfied, n (%)	2 (2.0)	9 (9.0)	
Very dissatisfied, n (%)	0 (0.0)	3 (3.0)	
Satisfaction score, mean \pm SD	4.3 \pm 0.8	3.9 \pm 1.1	0.003*

Significant difference between opioid-sparing vs. control group (p<0.05)

Discussion

The present study provides robust evidence supporting the superiority of opioid-sparing analgesia techniques over traditional opioid-based approaches in postoperative pain management. The significant reduction in opioid consumption (50% lower, p<0.001) aligns with findings from several recent large-scale studies investigating multimodal analgesic approaches. A meta-analysis by Wick et al. [11] involving 1,805 patients across 15 randomized controlled trials reported a similar 48% reduction in opioid consumption (95% CI: 38-57%, p<0.001) using multimodal protocols. However, their analysis focused on specific surgical procedures, whereas our study demonstrated efficacy across a broader range of surgeries.

The lower postoperative pain scores observed in our opioid-sparing group (mean difference of 0.9-1.2 points on NRS, p<0.001) are consistent with those reported by Memtsoudis et al. [12] in their

multicenter study of 1,008 patients undergoing total joint arthroplasty. Their study showed a mean pain score reduction of 1.1 points (95% CI: 0.8-1.4, p<0.001) with multimodal analgesia compared to conventional opioid-based approaches.

The reduced incidence of opioid-related adverse events in our study, particularly postoperative nausea and vomiting (15% vs. 29%, p=0.016) and sedation (11% vs. 22%, p=0.035), is in line with findings from a systematic review by Dunkman et al. [13]. Their analysis of 28 studies (n=2,485) reported a similar reduction in nausea and vomiting (relative risk [RR] 0.62, 95% CI: 0.51-0.75, p<0.001) and sedation (RR 0.58, 95% CI: 0.42-0.79, p<0.001) with opioid-sparing approaches. However, they found a significant reduction in pruritus (RR 0.59, 95% CI: 0.45-0.78, p<0.001), which our study did not demonstrate (6% vs. 13%, p=0.085).

The accelerated recovery metrics in our study, including earlier ambulation (median difference 6 hours, $p < 0.001$) and shorter hospital stays (median reduction 1 day, $p < 0.001$), are consistent with findings from a large retrospective cohort study by Cozowicz et al. [14]. Their analysis of 1,318,165 patients undergoing total hip or knee arthroplasty showed that opioid-sparing multimodal analgesia was associated with a 12.4% reduction in length of stay (95% CI: 11.6-13.2%, $p < 0.001$) and a 10.8% increase in the likelihood of being discharged home (95% CI: 9.9-11.7%, $p < 0.001$).

In contrast to our findings, a randomized controlled trial by Kharasch et al. [15] involving 120 patients undergoing laparoscopic bariatric surgery found no significant differences in postoperative opioid consumption ($p = 0.26$), pain scores ($p = 0.18$), or adverse events ($p = 0.52$) between multimodal and conventional opioid analgesia groups. However, their study was limited by a small sample size and a focus on a single surgical procedure, potentially explaining the divergent results.

Our study's high patient satisfaction rates with opioid-sparing analgesia (90% satisfied/very satisfied vs. 74% in control group, $p = 0.002$) exceed those reported in similar studies. Nielsen et al. [16] found an 82% satisfaction rate with multimodal analgesia compared to 71% with opioid-based approaches ($p < 0.01$) in their prospective cohort study of 1,143 patients undergoing abdominal surgery.

Several limitations of our study warrant consideration. First, the single-center design may limit generalizability. Second, the 48-hour follow-up period precludes assessment of long-term outcomes and opioid use. Third, while we demonstrated significant reductions in opioid-related adverse events, we did not systematically assess the incidence of adverse effects related to non-opioid analgesics used in the multimodal regimen.

Our study provides compelling evidence for the effectiveness and safety of opioid-sparing analgesia in managing postoperative pain across a range of surgical procedures. The significant reductions in opioid consumption, pain scores, and adverse events, coupled with accelerated recovery and high patient satisfaction, support the widespread implementation of opioid-sparing protocols. Future research should focus on optimizing multimodal regimens for specific surgical procedures and patient populations, as well as assessing long-term outcomes and cost-effectiveness.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates the superiority of opioid-sparing analgesia over traditional opioid-based approaches for postoperative pain management.

The opioid-sparing group exhibited significantly lower opioid consumption (median 30 mg vs. 60 mg OMEs, $p < 0.001$), pain scores (mean difference 0.9-1.2 points, $p < 0.001$), and opioid-related adverse events (nausea: 15% vs. 29%, $p = 0.016$; sedation: 11% vs. 22%, $p = 0.035$) compared to the control group. Furthermore, the opioid-sparing approach was associated with accelerated recovery, including earlier ambulation (median 18 vs. 24 hours, $p < 0.001$) and shorter hospital stays (median 3 vs. 4 days, $p < 0.001$), as well as higher patient satisfaction (55% vs. 40% very satisfied, $p = 0.002$). These findings support the implementation of opioid-sparing protocols as a standard of care for postoperative pain management. Future research should focus on optimizing multimodal regimens and assessing long-term outcomes and cost-effectiveness.

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